

Analysis of heat stress in classrooms of different school building types

Type of school building of the Gründerzeit Period

32. Grundschule "Sieben Schwaben" in Dresden (Sachsen)

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Approach and goals

Climate change is leading to higher temperatures and more frequent heat waves, which is particularly dangerous for children under the age of 12. School classes are often in classrooms for more than six hours a day, which affects health, well-being and learning performance at high room temperatures. Since pupils can hardly influence the temperatures, they are particularly at risk. In addition, the school building stock is usually not designed for increasingly hot summers and tends to overheat anyway due to the large window areas of classrooms. The joint project KlimaKonform II therefore investigated how high the heat load is in classrooms of different school building types in Saxony, Saxony-Anhalt and Thuringia and which heat adaptation measures are particularly effective.

This study uses a combined approach to analyze heat stress and thermal comfort in seven schools. These include three schools from the Wilhelminian period (1870–1918) in Plauen, Dresden and Gera, two prefabricated schools (1970–1990) in Zeitz and Dresden, a school from the post-war period (1952) in Dresden and a newly built school, also in Dresden. The comparison can be used to determine which building types are particularly susceptible to extreme heat stress.

This profile reports on the results on heat stress and thermal comfort in the school building type of Gründerzeit construction, based on the 32. Grundschule in Dresden (Saxony).

The analysis follows the process shown in the diagram below and consists of several steps:

- **Step a: Selection of representative school buildings**
- **Step B: Temperature measurements in classrooms**
Continuous measurement of classroom and outdoor temperatures from June to the end of September 2024 in two classrooms per school.
- **Step C: Survey of pupils and teachers on the perceived heat stress**
At the same time, pupils and their teachers in the two classrooms per school were asked how they felt about the indoor climate in summer. The survey makes it possible to record temperature-dependent well-being.
- **Step D: Effectiveness analysis of heat adaptation via thermal building simulation**

In addition, detailed 3D models of the examined classrooms were created for thermal building simulations. In this way, the effectiveness of different adaptation measures can be tested and compared in simulations.

Linking these steps (a to d) ensures that both objectively measured and subjectively perceived aspects of thermal comfort are taken into account.

This profile focuses mainly on structural-technical and behavioural adaptation to reduce heat stress in classrooms. The equally relevant school organisational measures (location of the summer holiday period, shortened lessons, switching to cooler classrooms) and schoolyard design aspects are not the subject of this profile.

32. Grundschule in Dresden (Sachsen)

a General information about the school

Description

The 32nd primary school "Sieben Schwaben" of the city of Dresden (Saxony) is located in the district of Blasewitz. The school is a typical example of school building in the Wilhelminian period, which is characterized by thick walls and large windows. The classrooms have no external sun protection, only internal glare protection. The classroom studied is oriented to the southeast. The school was completely renovated from 1992 to 1995, so the double-glazed windows are 30 years old and lead to high heat input from solar radiation.

Source: Google Earth, 04/2024

Sources: Christoph Schünemann, 06/2024

General information

Type of school	Primary school
Design	Gründerzeit period
Address	Hofmannstraße 34 01277 Dresden
Status of the renovation	Unrenovated
Grade levels taken into account	4th Grade

Classroom South-East Façade (Room 210)

Window details	Floor space	50.4 m²
	Orientation of the windows	South-East
	Window glazing	Double glazing (30 years old)
	Shading	Internal glare protection only
	Ventilation	Windows that can be opened
	Exterior wall	Brick wall
	Interior wall	Brick wall
	Ceiling	Wooden beam ceiling

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b Survey of pupils on heat stress

Generelle Information

The pupils in a single class, room 210, were asked about their perception of heat stress on four different days. The room is used by 4th grade students. On a typical hot day (survey date: August 28, 2024), there were 23 students in the classroom, and on another typical hot day (survey date: August 14, 2024), there were 22 students.

Source: Christoph Schünemann, 06/2024

Hot day (28.08.2024)

Room 210 at 12:15

Exterior	28,1 °C
Interior	29,1 °C

Perceived Temperature

Well-being

Feeling of tiredness

The values in the pie chart show the number of responses in each class on the day of the survey.

● Cold ● Cool ● OK ● Warm ● Hot ● No information

Pie charts to compare the temperatures perceived by the students in both classrooms: on a typical summer day (left) and on a hot day (right).

● Very well ● Well ● OK ● Unwell ● Very unwell ● no information

Perceived thermal well-being was similar and low overall on both days.

● Not tired ● Something tired ● Very tired ● No information

The reported feeling of fatigue was similar in both rooms on both summer days and hot days.

Hot day (14.08.2024)

Room 210 at 12:15

Exterior	29,2 °C
Interior	27,2 °C

Perceived Temperature

Well-being

Feeling of tiredness

Measures taken during the survey

Room 210
Ventilation through open window and fan

Room 210
Cross ventilation through open door and window

Conclusion

The perceived heat stress is critical on both hot days, which is reflected in both temperature perception and well-being. Unfortunately, there is no survey data for a summer day for the 32nd primary school as a comparison. The fact that the room temperatures for the survey are lower or in the range of outside temperatures indicates that a lack of window ventilation is not the reason for the heat stress in the classroom.

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c Temperature measurements and simulations in the classroom

Outdoor temperature measurement with KLIPS sensor

- Outside temperature
- School operations

The outside temperature was measured in the summer of 2024 with a [KLIPS](#) temperature sensor located 200 m from the school. The outside temperature curve from August 5 to September 11, 2024 is shown. This study period was characterized by extreme heat, with 15 hot days (maximum outside temperature above 30 °C), 2 tropical nights (minimum outside temperature at night above 20 °C) and 16 warm nights (minimum outside temperature at night above 18 °C).

Classroom interior measurements

- School operations
- Room temperature 210
- Outside temperature

Between August 5 and September 11, 2024, the room temperature in the classroom exceeded the critical limit of 30 °C eleven times and was almost continuously above the comfort temperature of 26 °C. The maximum temperature for the room was about 31.5 °C. Due to its south-east orientation and lack of sun protection devices, the classroom is exposed to a high heat load. This is also reflected in the rapid rise in room temperatures in the early morning hours.

Thermal building simulations of the current state (classroom 210)

3-dimensional model of the both classrooms in the thermal building simulation

The comparison of the simulated room temperature curve with the measured room temperature curve in the actual state is satisfactory, using the local climate and the assumption that in the period from 8:00 to 14:00 (weekdays) two windows and the classroom door are open when the outside temperature is less than the room temperature and two more windows are opened every 10 minutes for fresh air supply (regardless of the room temperature).

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d Effectiveness of heat adaptation measures and recommendations

Simulations of measures for heat adaptation

Effectiveness of adaptation measures to reduce heat stress

The bar diagram shows the overtemperature degree hours (ÜTG) for different simulation variants of both classrooms. The ÜTG are an indication of how many hours and how much the comfort temperature of 26 °C per year (Kh/a) is exceeded in the classroom. While v0 represents the reference (actual state) of the room, the other variants show the following differences:

Significant decrease in ÜTG in room 210 with external sun protection, which shows the high effectiveness of this in reducing heat stress (v1).

Solar control glazing is also very effective (v2).

Automatic day and night ventilation (v4) is also effective as it lets cool outside air in at night.

Temperature curves of classroom 210 for different variants

The temperature curve for room 210 on the left also illustrates the above results. With the external venetian blind, the heat load is significantly lower, about 5 °C lower. However, as in the graph above, window ventilation is ineffective and corresponds to the curve of V0.

Recommendations

The measurements, surveys, simulations and comparison with the classrooms of other school buildings lead to the following assessment and recommendation regarding the reduction of heat stress:

In the 32nd primary school, classrooms on the east side (street side) in particular are heavily exposed to heat, with temperatures of up to 31 °C. This is mainly due to the large window areas of the classrooms with older double glazing, which have a high total energy transmittance for solar radiation. Replacing the windows with solar control glazing would lead to a significant reduction in heat stress. External shading is even more effective. The ventilation behaviour in classroom 210 is already very well adapted to the heat. A possible night-time automatic window ventilation should be considered when renewing the windows, because this is also very effective for heat reduction. A combination of structural and technical measures together with adapted behaviour and school organisational measures can significantly reduce heat stress in classrooms.

General recommendations, derived from the comparison of the school buildings examined, can be found here: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19651356>